

SHAPING ANALYSIS OF A NON-CRIMP 3D ORTHOGONAL WEAVE E-GLASS COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT

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Abstract

In this work, the formability of a single layer E-glass non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven reinforcement (commercialized under trademark 3WEAVE[®] by 3Tex Inc.), is experimentally investigated. The study involves the shaping process of the 3D fabric on two moulds, namely tetrahedral and double-dome shape. The tests are assisted by 3D digital image correlation technique to have a continuous measurement of the local deformation during forming processes.

The obtained results represent useful information and comparison to predictive numerical modelling of the forming process with such 3D composite reinforcement.

1 Introduction

The manufacturing process of composite reinforcements has a crucial step in forming of a flat textile into a three-dimensional shape, the so-called preform. After shaping, the preform is injected with resin and consolidated. The shape of the preform is generally obtained by a punch and die forming process [1]. An important knowledge is the deformation mechanisms occurring during such processes. This is useful in predicting the permeability of the preform and the mechanical quality of the composite component [1].

3D orthogonal interlock woven reinforcements are used in the composites industry for a broad range of applications [2]. In spite of the fast growing interest, their deformation properties are not deeply known and investigated. Recent papers ([3] and [4]) detail experimental data and numerical

modelling of the deformability of an angle interlock carbon fabrics.

3D orthogonal woven reinforcements, with a specific geometry of Z-binding and extreme straightness of the stuffing warp and weft yarns were investigated observing the internal geometry and the response to static and cyclic loading ([5], [6], [7]).

In this work, the formability of a single layer E-glass non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven reinforcement (commercialized under trademark 3WEAVE[®] by 3Tex Inc.), is investigated. The study involves the experimental simulation of forming process of the 3D fabric on two moulds having the shape of tetrahedron and double-dome. The tests are assisted by 3D digital image correlation technique to have a continuous measurement of the local 3D displacement during forming processes. The obtained DIC measurements allow to evaluate the shear angle distribution, being this considered one of the main responsible of defects like wrinkles ([8], [9]).

2 Non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven reinforcement

The fabric is a single layer E-glass non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven reinforcement (commercialized under trademark 3WEAVE[®] by 3Tex Inc.). The yarns architecture of the preform has three warp and four weft layers, interlaced by through thickness (Z-directional) yarns (Fig. 1 [7]).

Fig. 1. Architecture of the tows inside the non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave preform [7]: (a) picture and (b) scheme of the unit cell.

	Fabric plies	1
	Areal density (g/m²)	3255
Warp	Insertion density (ends/cm)	2.76
	Top and bottom layer yarns (tex)	2275
	Middle layer yarns (tex)	1100
Weft	Insertion density (ends/cm)	2.64
	Yarns (tex)	1470
Z-yarns	Insertion density (ends/cm)	2.76
	Yarns (tex)	1800

Table 1. Properties of the non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave preform. Data provided by 3Tex Inc.

The fabric construction results in ~49%/~49%/~2% ratio of the fiber amounts (by volume) in the warp, weft and Z fiber directions, respectively. The same 3D glass reinforcement was adopted in the composite material for static and cyclic loading response in [7], [10] and [11]. A detailed description of the 3-D orthogonal weaving production process is presented in [12].

Fig. 2. Forming test set up: (a) tetrahedral shape; (b) double-dome shape.

The fibre material is PPG Hybon 2022 E-glass. Some features of the non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave reinforcement are listed in Table 1. A detailed measurement with optical microscopy and micro-CT of the preform architecture is presented in [6].

Furthermore, the mechanical behaviour under biaxial tensile and shear loading of the E-glass non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven reinforcement is described in [13].

3 Experimental set-up

Textile reinforcements allow to manufacture composite structures with complex shapes, for example by the RTM (Resin Transfer Moulding) process. The first stage of this process consists in a shaping, generally obtained by a punch and die process, of a flat textile reinforcement before resin injection [1]. In case of double curved shapes, the forming process involves in-plane deformations of the reinforcement and especially in-plane shear strain [4]. A successful manufacturing of a composite component must avoid forming of defects, i.e. wrinkles. Experimental analyses and numerical simulations can help to understand the conditions to improve forming processes.

To experimentally simulate a composite reinforcement forming process, the set-up illustrated in Fig. 2 was adopted. It consists of metallic components and an optical part. The steel components are a punch with a complex shape (i.e. tetrahedral and double-dome), and a metal holder to support the composite reinforcement. Geometry and dimensions of the tools are illustrated in Fig. 3. The optical part of the set-up consists of a stereo vision system (see Fig. 2), which acquires digital images of the forming process at a frequency of 1 Hz. These images are the basis for subsequent 3D image correlation by MatchID3D software (KAHOSL, Belgium [14]). The main benefit of this technique is measurement of the displacement field via a contactless method. For this purpose, the 3D textile specimen surface is speckled with black and white acrylic paints. One drawback of DIC technique could be the degradation of the pattern in the high deformed zones resulting in localized lack of correlation [15].

A rectangular reinforcement specimen (500 x 600 mm) is placed unclamped on the holder (see Fig. 2).

The load cell, which holds the punch, moves downwards for about 65 mm at a constant rate of 10 mm/min, from its initial zero position (which is maintained throughout all the tests). The tetrahedral and double-dome punches are mounted on an Instron 5567 tensile machine (see Fig. 2) with 30 kN load cell. Four tests are performed for the tetrahedral shape whose preform samples had warp and weft yarns parallel to the sides of the rectangular holder (0°/90°). For the double-dome mould were used three specimens with initial orientation of the in-plane yarns 0°/90° and two specimens with ±45° with respect to the sides of the rectangular holder.

Fig. 3. Forming tools geometry: (a) tetrahedron; (b) double-dome.

4 Results

Being the shear deformation considered as the primary deformation mechanism in the

reinforcement forming [8], the local shear angle is calculated by means the ‘grid method’ presented in [16] and [17]. The grid consists of facets, made by the spacing of the points (i.e. step size in pixels) in the Area of Interest (AoI) analyzed during 3D digital image correlation. For each recorded incremental position of the mould, the 3D displacement in the field of view of the cameras is obtained with DIC. The post-processing of the recorded displacements allows the calculation of the local shear angle as variation, with respect to the un-deformed shape, of the angle between sides or diagonals of facets according to the initial orientations of the warp and weft yarns in the reinforcement.

Fig. 4. Tetrahedral shape forming test. (a) Displacement field on the reinforcement surface by 3D DIC; (b) deformed shape of the 3D reinforcement at the end of shaping process.

4.1 Tetrahedral shape forming

The displacement field obtained by 3D DIC on the observed AoI surface is depicted in Fig. 4a and compared to the deformed shape of one specimen at the end of tetrahedral shape forming process (Fig. 4b).

The contour plot in Fig. 5 shows the map of the shear angles on the 3D reinforcement. This complex shape deforms the 3D textile in such a way that the higher shear angles are lower than 28 deg, at the conclusion of the forming process. The measured shear angles distribution on the 3D reinforcement is similar to that observed and numerically predicted in [4] for the tetrahedral shape forming of an interlock carbon fabric.

It is particularly interesting to notice an absence of wrinkles in the tetrahedral shape forming of the 3D reinforcement (see Fig. 4b), even though blank holder was not adopted.

Fig. 5. Tetrahedral shape forming test. Shear angle distribution at the end of shaping process.

4.2 Double-dome shape forming

The forming process of a double-dome shape with the considered 3D reinforcement generates the displacement distribution in Fig. 6, for both orientations of the yarns with respect to the sides of the rectangular holder.

The shaping does not generates wrinkles in the 3D reinforcement (see Fig. 7).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Double-dome forming process. Displacement field by 3D DIC on the reinforcement surface at the end of shaping process, for a specimen with initial yarns orientation: (a) $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and (b) $\pm 45^\circ$.

Fig. 7. Double-dome forming process.. Deformed shape of a specimen with initial yarns orientation $0^\circ/90^\circ$, at the end of shaping process.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. Double-dome forming test. Shear angle distribution at the end of shaping process for a specimen with initial yarns orientation: (a) $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and (b) $\pm 45^\circ$.

The 3D displacement field is adopted to evaluate the distribution of the shear angle on the reinforcement external surface at the end of forming process. The contour maps of the shear angle are in Fig. 8 for double-dome shapes obtained with the yarn orientations of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$. For a blank oriented at $0^\circ/90^\circ$, higher concentrations of shear angles are located in the higher curvature part (bottom right and left zones of picture in Fig. 8a). The maximum shear angle recorded in this case does not exceed about 24° in the final shape. The map of shear angles reported in Fig. 8b shows that

when specimen is initially oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$, the shear angle distribution on the reinforcement is also rotated of 45° . Therefore, the maximum shear angle has the same magnitude, mentioned above, and is located in the higher curvature part (bottom central zone of picture in Fig. 8b).

The behaviour during double-dome forming of the 3D glass reinforcement is similar to that of a twill 2/2 glass-PP fabric reported in [18]. The discrepancies, mainly in the magnitude of the shear angle, are explained by the different weaving architecture of the reinforcements. Indeed, differently from the twill 2/2 fabric, the presence and density of the Z-yarns in the 3D fabric, introduce an obstacle to the rotation of the in-plane yarns and as consequence a reduction the shear deformation.

5 Conclusions

The experimental study presented in this paper was focused on the formability of a single layer non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave E-glass composite reinforcement, commercialized under trademark 3WEAVE[®] by 3Tex Inc. The forming process was investigated with two complex shapes, namely double-dome and tetrahedron. The 3D digital images correlation technique allowed measuring the 3D displacement field on the reinforcement surface during shaping. Post-processing of these measurements provides the shear angle distribution in the AoI adopted for the DIC analysis. This is a relevant knowledge being the shear behaviour of a textile one of the main responsible of defects like wrinkles.

The obtained experimental results represent a data set including information on the deformation behaviour of the considered 3D reinforcement during forming of complex three-dimensional shapes. This is very useful on one side to investigate the capacities of the 3D reinforcement of delaying the onset of defects in draping complex forms; on the other to assess numerical modelling accuracy in predicting the behaviour of 3D reinforcement during complex shaping processes [19].

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